

Voltammetric Behaviour of Ascorbic Acid at the DME

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Differential pulse polarographic study of the anodic oxidation of ascorbic acid has been made over a pH range 3–11 in Britton–Robinson buffer medium. The nature of the limiting current has been evaluated by observing the influence of mercury pressure on the wave height of the dc polarograms. The number of electrons involved in the electrode process was confirmed by varying the pulse amplitude and noticing the $w_{1/2}$ in the DP polarograms. In acidic medium, the electrode reaction involves reversible oxidation of ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid. Two peaks appear in the DP polarograms in the alkaline medium due to establishment of an equilibrium between the acid anion and its hydrated form. Both the forms get oxidised at different potentials.

THE polarographic wave of ascorbic acid has been utilised for its estimation in various media.

Kajita and Senda¹ have applied polarography in simultaneous determination of ascorbic acid and erythorbic acid. Falat and Cheng² have studied the comparative behaviour of ascorbic acid and dopamine by voltammetry employing an electrochemically treated graphite/epoxy electrode. Fogg and Summan³ have monitored ascorbic acid contents in accelerated light degradation studied by differential pulse polarography. Sawyer *et al.*⁴ have made a cyclic voltammetric study of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid in dimethylformamide at a platinum electrode. The anodic oxidation of ascorbic acid has been studied mainly in acidic pH range wherein ascorbic acid gives an anodic polarographic wave due to the oxidation of 'enediol' system; the wave shifts with pH⁵ towards negative potentials. The pH dependence of the half-wave potential has been investigated by several workers^{6–12}. Kolthoff and Lingane¹³ suggested that the anodic oxidation of ascorbic acid at the dropping mercury electrode (DME) results in the formation of dehydroascorbic acid. Cattaneo⁷ and Vavrin⁸ have assumed a reversible character for the oxidation wave of ascorbic acid. However, the fact that at all pH values, the polarographic $E_{1/2}$ is about 200 mV more positive than the equilibrium potential measured potentiometrically together with the non-reducibility of dehydroascorbic acid at DME, indicates an irreversible electrode process. Cattaneo⁷ accounted for the pH dependence of $E_{1/2}$ by suggesting that the irreversible oxidation is preceded by reversible dissociation of two protons. Heyrovsky¹⁴ explained the behaviour of ascorbic acid as a reversible oxidation to an unstable electroactive product which is then transformed to an electro-inactive dehydroascorbic acid by fast irreversible chemical reaction. Kern^{11,12} has also supported the above mechanism, but Koutecky¹⁵

regarded the transformation of active to inactive form as a reversible process. Perone and Kretlow¹⁶ assumed the succeeding chemical reaction as a hydration and have derived kinetic data by cyclic voltammetry and potential step electrolysis employing HMDE at pH 7.2. Lindquist¹⁷ has performed voltammetry employing C-paste electrode and suggested the oxidation of ascorbic acid as irreversible.

In spite of the above mentioned literature, pertaining to the anodic oxidation of ascorbic acid, there appears discrepancy about the mechanism of electrode reaction and the nature of anodic current. The authors have therefore made a systematic voltammetric study of the anodic oxidation of ascorbic acid over a wide pH range.

Experimental

Voltammetric measurements were made using a 174-A polarographic analyser (Princeton Applied Research, USA), in combination with an X-Y recorder (Houston 707) which recorded the polarograms. A cell having three-electrode assembly was used. A DME was used as the working electrode and a platinum wire acted as the auxiliary electrode. All the potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode.

Analytical grade reagents were used for all the experiments. Britton–Robinson buffers were used for maintaining the desired pH and as the supporting electrolyte. Ascorbic acid solution was prepared in double-distilled and deoxygenated water. Since aqueous ascorbic acid decomposes slowly, fresh stock solutions were prepared each time.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows dc polarograms of a 5×10^{-4} M ascorbic acid at pH 3.2, 5.0, 7.1, 8.0, 9.1 and 11.2.

Similarly, the DP polarograms of ascorbic acid in different pH media are shown in Fig. 2. The dc and DP peak characteristics are summarised in

Fig. 1. DC polarograms of ascorbic acid ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$), B—R buffer at pH (A) 3.2, (B) 5.05, (C) 7.1, (D) 8.0, (E) 9.1, (F) 11.2; temp. = 27° .

Fig. 2. DP polarograms of ascorbic acid ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$), B—R buffer at pH (A) 3.2, (B) 5.05, (C) 9.1, (D) 11.2; temp. = 27° , pulse amplitude = 25 mV s^{-1} , scan rate = 2 mV s^{-1} , drop time = 1 s.

Table 1. A profound change in the characteristics of the anodic wave with change in pH was observed at pH 7 and above wherein two waves or two peaks

appeared. The change of $E_{1/2}$ and E_p with pH indicates involvement of proton in the oxidation process.

The shift of peak towards more positive potential with increasing ascorbic acid concentration was observed in all pH media. A maximum shift of 50 mV was observed at pH 5 for the first peak whereas for the second peak a maximum shift of 85 mV was observed at pH 9.1 when the concentration was varied from 0.52×10^{-4} to $9.52 \times 10^{-4} M$. The relationship between the concentration and the DP peak current generally follows a straight line for the first peak. However, for the second peak, these plots did not follow a linear path. This indicates that the electrode process may be partly diffusion-controlled and partly kinetically controlled¹⁹. During the study of the influence of mercury pressure on wave height (dc polarogram) the plots of i_l vs $\sqrt{h}$ for both the wave yielded straight lines passing through the origin. Moreover, i_l vs h plots shows a curved plot instead of a horizontal line (characteristic of kinetically controlled limiting current²⁰). The electrode process thus appears diffusion-controlled.

The log-plot analyses of dc waves are shown in Fig 3. The slope values in the acidic region

Fig. 3. Log plot analysis of dc polarograms of ascorbic acid ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$), B—R buffer at pH (A) 3.2, (B) 5.05, (C) 8.0, (D and D') 9.1.

correspond to a 2-electron reversible process. The involvement of 2-electrons in the oxidation process is further confirmed by DPP experiments. A plot

TABLE 1—VOLTAMMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ASCORBIC ACID AT DIFFERENT pH

Concn = 5×10^{-4} M, pulse amplitude = 25 mV, scan rate = 2 mV s^{-1} , temp. = 27° , drop time = 1 s, B-R buffer

pH	$E_{1/2}$ (V)		i_L (μA)		Peak potential (V)		Peak current (μA)	
	I wave	II wave	I wave	II wave	I peak	II peak	I peak	II peak
3.2	+0.150	—	3.45	—	+0.175	—	30.00	—
5.0	+0.045	—	1.80	—	+0.050	—	15.00	—
7.1	-0.015	Indistin- guishable	3.85	1.30	-0.010	+0.220	31.00	14.75 (just a spike)
8.0	-0.055	Indistin- guishable	4.75	0.75	-0.050	+0.130	27.25	11.75
9.1	-0.080	+0.080	3.40	3.00	-0.070	+0.075	24.50	10.75
11.2	-0.240	-0.140	2.60	2.85	-0.230	-0.140	19.20	12.00

Fig. 4. DP polarograms of ascorbic acid at different pulse amplitude (ΔE); concn. = 1.04×10^{-4} M, B-R buffer pH = 5.05, temp. = 27° , scan rate = 2 mV s^{-1} , drop time = 1 s.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PULSE AMPLITUDE ON PEAK HALF-WIDTH

Concn. = 1.04×10^{-4} M ascorbic acid, scan rate = 2 mVs^{-1} , drop time 1 s, pH = 5.1, B-R buffer

Pulse amplitude (ΔE) mV	Peak half-width ($w_{1/2}$) mV	E_p V
5	71	+0.085
10	70	+0.080
25	65	+0.075
50	75	+0.060
100	100	+0.050

Fig. 5. Peak half-width vs pulse amplitude of DP polarograms of ascorbic acid (1.04×10^{-4} M).

of peak half-width ($w_{1/2}$) and pulse amplitude (ΔE) for a 1.04×10^{-4} M ascorbic acid at pH 5.1 was made. The peak half-width values calculated from the DP polarograms (Fig. 4) are given in Table 2. A comparison of experimental $w_{1/2}$ vs ΔE plot (Fig. 5) with that of theoretical one at different n values as derived by Parry and Osteryoung¹⁸, indicates a reversible oxidation involving 2-electrons.

The possible oxidation sites on the ascorbic acid molecule are the two unsaturated C-2 and C-3 atoms. Thus in acidic medium the electrode reaction involves a reversible oxidation to dehydroascorbic acid. The splitting of the wave in alkaline pH region may be due to the hydration of ascorbic acid at pH > 7. The hydrated species should be difficult to oxidise than the unhydrated form. The first wave appears to correspond to the oxidation of unhydrated species while the second wave results from the oxidation of the hydrated species. Thus two waves result due to a sluggishly-held equilibrium between the hydrated and anhydrous species. The probable mechanisms of oxidation in acidic and alkaline media are given below.

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ACIDIC MEDIA

ALKALINE MEDIA

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